

Parallel/distributed intelligent hyperparameters search for generative artificial neural networks

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Abstract. This article presents a parallel/distributed methodology for the intelligent search of the hyperparameters configuration for generative artificial neural networks (GANs). Finding the configuration that best fits a GAN for a specific problem is challenging because GANs simultaneously train two deep neural networks. Thus, in general, GANs have more configuration parameters than other deep learning methods. The proposed system applies the iterated racing approach taking advantage of parallel/distributed computing for the efficient use of resources for configuration. The main results of the experimental evaluation performed on the MNIST dataset showed that the parallel system is able to efficiently use the GPU, achieving a high level of parallelism and reducing the computational wall clock time by 78%, while providing competitive comparable results to the sequential hyperparameters search.

Keywords: Hyperparameters search · Artificial Neural Networks · Generative Adversarial Networks · Iterated race

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1 Introduction

Generative Adversarial Networks (GANs) are emerging powerful methods to train deep generative models. GANs have demonstrated being a successful tool for many applications, especially those concerning multimedia information (e.g., images, sound, and video), science, healthcare, and other areas [10,18,23].

To construct a generative model, GAN training considers two artificial neural networks (ANN), a generator and a discriminator, that apply adversarial learning to optimize their parameters by defining a minmax optimization problem. The mark of a successful GAN is a generator that produces accurate synthetic samples. However, during GAN training, the adversarial dynamics may give rise to different convergence pathologies, e.g., gradient vanishing and mode collapse [3]. Co-evolutionary training methods have shown to be resilient to the degenerative behavior of GAN training by evolving two populations of ANN (one of generators against one of discriminators) towards convergence.

This work focuses on Lipizzaner [20], a GAN library that applies a spatially distributed co-evolutionary training method to addresses the minmax optimization problems by fostering arms races between the populations. The appropriate selection of hyperparameters strongly determines the success of deep learning methods. When dealing with GANs, that simultaneously train two ANN, picking the correct configuration for the hyperparameters is even more critical.

In this line of work, this article proposes a parallel/distributed system for the automatic configuration of relevant GAN parameters, implemented over a high performance computing infrastructure. The proposed system applies a two-level parallel approach, combining distributed memory and shared memory GPU-based training, to efficiently execute the hyperparameters search proposed by *iterated racing* (IRACE), a well-known configuration tool for tuning optimization algorithms [13].

IRACE implements an iterated racing algorithm to search through the parameter space, looking for a configuration that minimizes the experiment target function. A race is a competition between a set of candidate configurations where individual parameters are drawn from independent normal distributions. During a race, configurations that perform statistically worse than the rest are discarded as soon as possible. Candidate configurations are compared with non-parametric Friedman’s two-way analysis of variance by ranks. Races are performed until the specified computation budget is exhausted. Surviving configurations proceed to the next race and bias sampling distributions towards themselves.

In the proposed system, the iterated race approach is distributed to efficiently search the parameter space of GANs, to provide a useful high-level configuration algorithm capable of taking advantage of the computing power of large supercomputing facilities. The main training parameters in Lipizzaner are studied: the *initial learning rate* (the step size of the change of the weights), the *number of steps the discriminator skips learning*, to avoid early convergence and subpar results due to vanishing gradient issues, the *mutation probability*, and the *standard deviation* of the normal distribution used in the Gaussian mutation.

Configuration experiments are performed for a standard image processing problem: the generation of handwritten digits. Training data are 60,000 grayscale images of handwritten digits from the MNIST dataset. Experiments are performed on the infrastructure provided by National Supercomputing Center Uruguay [17]. The accuracy of the obtained generative model is measured in terms of Frechet inception distance score, a black box, discriminator-independent

metric, that computes image similarity of the synthesized samples to the samples in the training dataset. In any case, the proposed methodology can be applied to study the configuration of GANs for other relevant applications, such as the parallel/distributed GAN for data augmentation of COVID-19 training images [24].

The contributions of the research are the implementation and validation of an automatic procedure to efficiently search the Lipizzaner parametric space. The proposed methodology will allow computing the most effective parameter values, significantly reducing the execution time demanded by brute force approaches.

The article is organized as follows. Section 2 introduces the subject of automatic hyperparameter configuration in GANs, it presents the main software components devised and used in our research, and it briefly presents a review of related works. Section 3 describes the proposed parallel/distributed approach to automatically tune GANs. The experimental evaluation and results are reported and discussed in Section 4. Finally, the conclusions and the main lines for future work are presented in Section 5.

2 Automatic parameter configuration of GANs

This section describes the approach for automatic parameter configuration of GANs and the software libraries used in the proposed system. It also presents a review of related works.

2.1 Parameter configuration of GANs

In the machine learning domain, the selection of the appropriate hyperparameter configuration has been a subject of study over the years [15,22,28]. Hyperparameter optimization methods can be grouped into two main groups: manual exploration-based approaches, which usually are led by expert knowledge; and automatic search-based methods, such as, random, grid, and racing search [4]. The number of parameters to configure machine learning algorithms and the alternatives for each parameter are extremely large. Therefore, the hyperparameter optimization problem deals with high-dimensional search spaces. Besides, most methods are based on trial-and-error, which means that they need to run the algorithm and evaluate numerically its accuracy to assess the tentative solution (hyperparameter configuration), which in general is very time consuming. The search huge search space and the time consuming evaluation process severely affects the application of the search of hyperparameters.

This research focuses on the use of racing hyperparameter search methods. Racing search methods allow the rapid search of *good* hyperparameter configurations [6]. These search algorithms define a race among different tentative hyperparameter configurations and keep in the race the most promising configurations, while discarding the least competitive ones. The racing method allows an efficient use of computational resources by guiding the search through the search space area that defines the most promising hyperparameters configurations.

This article aims at solving the problem of automatically tuning the hyperparameters that command the algorithm of GAN training. In order to obtain a generative model, GANs train two deep neural networks: the generative model (*generator*) and a discriminative model (*discriminator*), which apply an adversarial learning to learn from each other [10]. As most of deep learning approaches, the network weights of both the generator and the discriminator are updated/optimized by using a variation of stochastic gradient decent approach. Therefore, the complexity of finding the hyperparameter configuration that best fit algorithm is rather more difficult than in other deep learning methods, because GANs consider the simultaneous training of two different deep neural networks.

GANs are notoriously hard to train, frequently showing degenerative behaviors or pathologies, such as mode collapse or vanishing gradients [29,2]. In order to mitigate these problems, different approaches inspired on co-evolutionary algorithms have been proposed, e.g., Lipizzaner [21] or Mustangs [25]. Thus, this article proposes using an automatic hyperparameter configuration method for Lipizzaner algorithm.

2.2 Software libraries used in the proposed system

This subsection describes the software components integrated in the proposed parallel system.

Lipizzaner. In our study, Lipizzaner GAN training framework is used to train the generative models [21]. Lipizzaner implements a co-evolutionary distributed GAN training method, in which two set of generations (i.e., populations) are trained against each other, one for generators and one for discriminators. The networks (i.e., individuals in each population) are located in a two-dimensional spatial grid. The concept of neighborhood is applied to define those individuals that participate in the training phase for both generators and discriminators. Lipizzaner has shown to be effective overcoming the main pathologies in GAN training (e.g., mode collapse and non-convergence). In turn, cellular training allows implementing a data-parallel approach where each cell is trained using reduced subsets of training dataset, allowing to improve the computational efficiency of the training process because less training data batches are needed, while providing comparable quality results [26].

IRACE. The IRACE software package is an automatic hyperparameter configurator based on a racing procedure [13]. It was initially devised to tune meta-heuristic optimization algorithms, which the quality of their solutions are highly dependent on their configurations. In IRACE, a race consists of three steps: i) sampling new parametric configurations, ii) testing configurations on the target algorithm, iii) discard configurations that are outperformed as soon as possible. At the end of the race, the sampling distribution is biased towards the best parameters and the process is repeated.

Linking IRACE and Lipizzaner. The search logic implemented by IRACE is abstracted from the specific domain problem. A middleware component named *target runner* is required to allow communication between IRACE and the algorithm to be optimized. This component is responsible for testing parametric configurations sent by IRACE on Lipizzaner, and returning the results back. It is also the target runner responsibility to verify that the minimum required resources to run Lipizzaner are available before execution.

2.3 Related work

The hyperparameter optimization manually carried out by human experts requires bounded computational resources. Humans can easily and quickly appreciate poor hyperparameter configurations by examining the stochastic gradient descent results after a few steps. This is helpful to rapidly terminate training of algorithms that are performing bad due to the hyperparameter selection. However, the use of human experts have some disadvantages: it is time intense of human effort, few design alternatives and hyperparameter settings are explored, and the configurations are typically evaluated only on limited set of instances.

Automatic hyperparameter configuration search algorithms have been proposed to overcome the drawbacks of manual search [31]. The most intuitive approach is the grid or Cartesian hyperparameter search [5]. This method makes an exhaustive search of the best configuration by evaluating each combination of possible values of hyperparameters. The evaluation is carried out according to a predefined performance metric and using cross validation. This method can theoretically find the best (global optimum) hyperparameter configuration. However, the number of parameters and their range of values make the use of grid search computationally cost prohibitive.

Random search algorithms have been proposed to sample the hyperparameters search space. Basically, it tries random combinations of a range of values. His search is less expensive (in terms of computational cost) than grid search [5]. Thus, it is more efficient in high-dimensional hyperparameters spaces. However, it has been shown that random search is unreliable for finding hyperparameters for some complex models [5].

Finding the hyperparameter configuration that best fit an algorithm to solve a given problem can be defined as an optimization problem where the objective function is a black-box function. However, classic optimization approaches such as the ones based on the gradient descent or Newton methods are impractical to address the hyperparameter configuration problem. Thus, some authors have proposed different optimization techniques to tune hyperparameters in machine learning, such as metaheuristics [1] or Bayesian optimization [28] methods.

A number of studies have focused on using metaheuristics to configure hyperparameters in deep neural networks [1]. For example, a convolutional neural network classifier for tumor-specific microRNA signatures was configured by using an evolutionary algorithm (EA) [16]. In this approach, the authors tuned 10 hyperparameters and the quality of the configuration was evaluated on a 10-fold validation process. The same type of neural network, a CNN, was tuned

by using another EA [11]. In this case the authors considered nine hyperparameters and they evaluated their approach over different image datasets such as, MNIST and CIFAR. Besides, metaheuristics have been applied to address the same problem with other deep neural networks, such as, recurrent neural networks (RNN). For example, evolutionary strategies (ES) were used to find the best configuration of RNNs taking into account the hyperparameters that define the network architecture and the look back for addressing synthetic [7] and car park occupancy [8] forecasting problems.

Bayesian optimization has shown being an effective method to solve hyperparameter optimization [30]. Bayesian optimization was used to configure CNNs to address the classification on CIFAR image dataset [28]. In this case, the authors optimized four hyperparameters of the CNN learning algorithm (including the DNN depth). This type of hyperparameter optimization method was applied to configure an RNN applied to estimate the disaggregation household power consumption forecasting (i.e., predict the power load signal per appliance) [12].

Racing hyperparameter configuration methods emerged as automatic tuning methods that find good configurations through statistically guided experimental evaluations [6]. The main idea is that the method defines a race of sequentially generated candidate configurations, evaluates them via several independent runs, and discards the less competitive ones as soon as there is a statistically evidence that is performing worst than the other configurations. Removing from the race the least promising solutions improves the search, allows evaluating promising configurations on more instances, and obtaining reliable estimates of their behavior. An example of racing algorithm is the F-race, which is based on racing and Friedman’s non-parametric two-way analysis of variance by ranks [6].

An improvement over F-race is the iterative F-race (I/F-race), which is the method implemented by IRACE and it is applied in our study. In this case, the set of initial tentative configurations are created by sampling the parameter space and, when there is a statistical evidence that a configuration is performing worse than the best ones, this worst configuration is discarded, and a new configuration is generated by randomly modifying the best ones [13]. This method allows to speed up the search providing comparative results, while critically reducing the computational costs. At the time of writing this article, racing methods (such as the one implemented in IRACE) have not been applied to deal with deep learning methods, but to machine learning (mainly to tune metaheuristics) [14,19,27].

This article proposes applying an automatic approach to tune GANs. The main differences of our approach regarding the current state of the art are that (a) an automatic tool is applied to configure the hyperparameters of GAN training algorithm and (b) IRACE is used to explore the tentative configurations of such special type of machine learning/deep learning approach.

3 The proposed parallel/distributed approach for hyperparameters search

This section describes the proposed approach for parallel/distributed search of hyperparameters values of GANs.

3.1 Overall description

The proposed system integrates IRACE, Lipizzaner, and parallel programming in distributed memory platforms. The building block for the proposed system is the traditional sequential search for hyperparameters implemented in IRACE, as described in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1: Sequential hyperparameters search.

During a race, the sequential approach of IRACE executes one parametric configuration at a time. The race algorithm implemented by IRACE evaluates surviving parametric configurations on a fixed number of instances before performing the applied statistical comparison. As a consequence, the evaluation of several instances is suitable for parallelism, by applying the domain decomposition approach. Furthermore, as the executions are independent, no data or control communications are required between processes.

Three parallel schemes are supported by IRACE to perform fixed executions. The *parallel processes* scheme is based on creating multiple spawn processes using the parallel R package. The *MPI* scheme applies a distributed memory approach, where parallel processes are controlled using the Message Passing Interface protocol. Both previous schemes are mainly conceived for interactive processing. Finally, the *batch jobs cluster* parallel scheme allows off-line process execution by using submission scripts of standard workload management systems (Torque, SLURM, etc.) to submit multiple executions of the target algorithm as independent jobs. The off-line execution is supported by submissions to a batch queue and waiting for processes to finish. In any case, the number of parallel call is configurable.

The proposed parallel approach for hyperparameters search of GANs is based on the parallel process scheme of IRACE. The basic schema proposed for execution on a single computer/server is extended for proper execution on a larger,

non-dedicated infrastructure, such as the one available in modern supercomputing centers. This type of facilities has a very important impact on e-Science by promoting a collaborative approach where financial resources is scarce, such as in Latin America [9].

For execution on a large, shared computing infrastructure, parallel processes that share limited resources (e.g., GPU, RAM memory, and ports for communication) must be properly controlled. In consequence, a new component is incorporated in the solution architecture, the *Execution Manager*. The main job of the Execution Manager is monitoring the execution environment and taking proper decisions to allow or stop IRACE from launching new Lipizzaner instances, based on the available computing resources. Two specific resources are monitored and evaluated: i) the number of available GPU and the free GPU memory on each one, and ii) the availability of network ports for communication between master and slave processes in Lipizzaner.

Thus, the proposed parallel search requires two new parameters as input:

1. The GPU memory required to run a single instance of Lipizzaner, and
2. The range of port numbers where Lipizzaner instances are allowed to attach.

In the developed implementation of the parallel approach, the Execution Manager is a Python class pickled in the filesystem. The responsibility for changing and saving the Execution Manager state is delegated to runners. This design decision guarantee that every runner is able to read the Execution Manager in a safe way by locking the pickle file. Thus, specific modifications are required in the parallel version of the Lipizzaner runner algorithm.

The developed parallel version of the Lipizzaner runner is detailed in Algorithm 1.

Algorithm 1 Lipizzaner runner algorithm in the parallel search approach

Require: learning rate, α , μ , skip steps

```

1: finish = False
2: while finish is not True do
3:   resources = executionManager.allocateResources()
4:   if resources is not None then
5:     config = prepareLipizzaner(lr,  $\alpha$ ,  $\mu$ , skip_steps)
6:     score = runLipizzaner(config)
7:     executionManager.freeResources()
8:     finish = True
9:   else
10:    sleep()
11:   end if
12: end while
13: return score

```

Algorithm 1 requires four parameters to set up the Lipizzaner configuration file. These parameters are sent by IRACE to test a specific parametric configuration on Lipizzaner and are explained in subsection 4. The main body of the runner algorithm is the loop in lines 2–12. The iteration is performed until Lipizzaner results are retrieved (line 6) and the resources have been released (line 7). If there are no available resources to allocate (line 9), the runner process sleeps between 15 and 30 seconds before a new try (line 10). Finally, the score is returned.

Fig. 2 shows a diagram of the parallel architecture. The main software components are identified and data flows between processes are represented by directed arrows.

4 Experimental evaluation

This section describes the experimental evaluation of the proposed parallel approach for the intelligent search of Lipizzaner hyperparameters.

Fig. 2: The implemented parallel hyperparameters search.

4.1 Evaluation methodology

Methodology. The experimental evaluation is focused on analyzing the execution time improvement of the parallel approach and the quality of the generated images during the search. The specific domain task is the MNIST handwritten digit generation, described in the next paragraph. The grid used for Lipizzaner has dimension 1×1 , which essentially trains a single pair of generator/discriminator networks with learning rate mutation. In order to evaluate parallelism, the computational efficiency results are studied, considering a sequential IRACE search as reference baseline. The speedup and scalability of the proposed system is evaluated by increasing the number of parallel executions of Lipizzaner to 2, 4, 6, and 8. The Execution Manager was constrained to allow up to 4 instances of Lipizzaner running on each GPU.

Generation task. The goal of the proposed GANs is to generate diverse and good quality images from the MNIST dataset. MNIST database is composed of 28×28 pixel images of handwritten digits. Digits are centered and size-normalized. The training dataset contains 60000 images and test dataset 10000.

Metrics. The Fréchet Inception Distance (FID) metric is used to assess the quality and diversity of generated images. The FID score is based on a hidden layer of the inception_v3 model, a deep convolutional neural network trained to classify images into 1000 classes. The FID is calculated in three steps: i) feed real and generated images through the inception network; ii) gather activations from the last hidden layer; and iii) compute the Fréchet distance between activations distributions. A lower FID indicates better-quality and more-diverse images. The computational efficiency is evaluated in terms of execution time and GPU usage.

The execution time is retrieved from the job accounting log file of the workload management system. GPU usage is gathered from the output of the *nvidia-smi* command, available in CUDA environments.

IRACE search. The Lipizzaner parameters to be explored in the search are: i) the initial learning rate (l_0) for the Adam optimization algorithm, ii) the Gaussian mutation probability (mu), i.e., the probability of mutating the current value of the Adam learning rate after each epoch; iii) the mutation regularization factor ($alpha$), which adjust the mean of the Gaussian mutation distribution; and iv) the number of updates to the generator network for each update of the discriminatory network ($skip_steps$). This parameter is used to avoid diminished gradient problems, as generator network is trained $skip_steps$ times before updating discriminator weights.

IRACE parameters. In order to perform a statistically robust search, IRACE constrains the minimum number of the target runner executions ($minBudget$). The $minBudget$ value is computed based on the number of parameters to be explored (n_params) as defined in Equation 1, where $minSurvival$ is the number of configurations needed to continue the execution of each race, n_iter is the number of races according to Equation 2, m is a parameter used to define the number of configurations sampled and evaluated at each iteration, $eachTest$ is the number of instances evaluated between elimination tests, and T_{new} is the number of new instances added to the execution list. The default values for the studied parameters are $minSurvival = 4$, $m = 5$, $eachTest = 1$, and $T_{new} = 1$.

$$minBudget = (minSurvival + 1) \times n_iter \times (m + eachTest + (n_iter - 1) \times \max(eachTest, T_{new})) \quad (1)$$

$$n_iter = 2 + \log_2(n_params) \quad (2)$$

The default parameter values of IRACE were used to explore four parameters of Lipizzaner, thus the $minBudget$ value defined by Equation 1 is 180. The maximum number of Lipizzaner executions for a whole search was set to 200.

Development and execution platform. The proposed system was implemented in Python 3.6 and R 4.1.0. Libraries used are Lipizzaner 1.0 and IRACE 3.4.1.9. The experimental analysis was performed on high-end servers with two Xeon Gold 6138 processors (40 cores each), two Nvidia Tesla P100 GPUs (12 GB memory), 128 GB RAM memory, and 10 GbE from National Supercomputing Center (Cluster-UY), Uruguay

4.2 Numerical results

This subsection reports the numerical results of the proposed parallel approach to explore the parameter space of Lipizzaner with IRACE.

Execution time. Table 1 reports the execution time of the proposed search for the five parallelization levels studied. The sequential approach required a considerable long time to complete the run (about 60 hours). Considering that a space of just four parameters is explored, this execution time can be prohibitive to complete accurate parameter configurations in reasonable execution times. Then, as the number of parallel Lipizzaner calls performed by IRACE increased, the execution time decreased. The best (minimum) value was 16.81 hours for the execution using 8 parallel calls. These execution time values demonstrate that the proposed system is able to reduce the wall time for configuration in a factor of $3.56\times$.

Table 1: Execution time results.

<i>experiment</i>	<i>execution time</i>
sequential	59.8 hs
2 parallel calls	41.5 hs
4 parallel calls	23.21 hs
6 parallel calls	20.05 hs
8 parallel calls	16.81 hs

Fig. 3: Speedup analysis.

The speedup analysis is reported in Fig. 3, showing that the execution time reduction is sub-linear with respect to the number of parallel calls. This behavior is mainly due to the non-determinism in the parallel execution, which generate idle times for processes and resources. In addition, the actual number of parallel processes is limited to the number of surviving configurations; in the final stages of a race, few parametric configurations are evaluated, thus searches with 4, 6, and 8 parallel calls achieve the same degree of parallelization. Finally, there is a relatively low overhead for communication with the Execution Manager.

Fig. 4 reports the number of completed Lipizzaner executions over time for each search. Results demonstrate the usefulness of the proposed approach, which is able to complete a significantly larger number of executions within a given time. For example, considering a time limit of 1000 min, the search using 8 parallel calls is able to complete 194 executions of Lipizzaner, whereas the sequential search is only able to complete 58. These results imply a significant better throughput of the parallel executions, improving $3.35\times$ over the sequential.

GPU memory utilization. Video cards are powerful and expensive hardware components that speed up the training process of deep learning algorithms. Then, optimizing the GPU utilization is desired to improve performance and reduce costs. Table 2 reports the workload of the two available GPUs (gpu0 and gpu1) during the experimental evaluation as the percentage of the total memory in use. Load values were gathered every 60 seconds using the NVIDIA System Management Interface.

Fig. 4: Number of Lipizzaner executions over time.

Load results do not follow a normal distribution, thus values of the median, interquantile range (IQR), and maximum are reported as relevant estimators in Table 2.

Table 2: GPU utilization percentage results.

<i>experiment</i>	<i>GPU</i>	<i>median</i>	<i>IQR</i>	<i>maximum</i>
sequential	gpu 0	10	6	26
	gpu 1	0	0	3
2 parallel calls	gpu 0	13	17	52
	gpu 1	0	0	3
4 parallel calls	gpu 0	26	36	87
	gpu 1	0	0	4
6 parallel calls	gpu 0	27	37	66
	gpu 1	0	19	51
8 parallel calls	gpu 0	34	35	71
	gpu 1	7	22	80

Results in Table 2 show that in experiments that executed less than four instances of Lipizzaner at a time, the second GPU (gpu1) remained idle, as the required video memory at every moment is below 12 GB. In contrast, in searches with 6 and 8 parallel calls, a single GPU cannot handle all processes and a proportion of the load is delegated to gpu1. As the number of parallel calls increases, load measures also increase, thus the system is able to make a better use of the available resources. The median of usage percentage distribution on gpu0 was 3.4 times greater on the 8 parallel calls search compared to the sequential search. On gpu 1, the 8 parallel calls had a load median of 7% and the maximum load reached 80%, whereas the sequential search never used a second GPU.

Lipizzaner results. The search tasks performed by the different experiments evaluated here are the same. However, the non-determinism of some of the operations carried out by IRACE influences on how the search evolves, and therefore, on the results computed by Lipizzaner. Thus, each experiment explored different hyperparameters and provided different FID scores. Here, we evaluate the whole distribution of the FID results returned by Lipizzaner during the search. Thus, Fig. 5 shows these results by showing the results in a histogram. The first group of the histogram (group 1) illustrates the frequency of the Lipizzaner configurations that returned FID scores between 0 and 99; the second, the frequency of FID scores between 100 and 199, and so on (i.e., the group i in the histogram represents the frequency of the Lipizzaner runs that provided $\text{FID} \in [(i - 1) \times 100, (i \times 100) - 1]$).

According to the histograms in Fig. 5, there is not a significance difference among the distributions of the results of the five experiments. All histograms show that most of Lipizzaner configurations computed during the search provide FID scores in the first decile, i.e., between 0 and 99. Thus, this confirms that, even the stochastic nature of IRACE search, all the experiments carried out a similar hyperparameters search.

Fig. 5: FID histograms of Lipizzaner executions.

Finally, Fig. 6 presents images generated during different iterations of the IRACE by using 8 parallel calls search. This figure allows the reader to observe the quality and diversity of the samples according to the FID score. It can be seen that with FID score 1061, the generator produces only noise; when the FID decreases to 380, the quality of the samples improves but the diversity is still limited; and with FID score 55, the generator synthesizes better quality and diversity digits (images).

5 Conclusions and future work

This article presented a proposal for a parallel intelligent hyperparameters search for generative artificial neural networks. The proposed implementation is an automatic procedure to efficiently search through the hyperparameter space of Lipizzaner by the means of racing. The main goal of the parallel approach is to reduce the execution time required to perform a parameters search using IRACE and maximize the use of available resources. This goal was achieved by parallelizing independent executions of Lipizzaner in a controlled way, using middleware components that manage Lipizzaner processes and monitor the GPU memory utilization.

Fig. 6: Generated images (digits) during the 8 parallel calls search.

Experimental evaluation results showed that the parallel system was able to significantly reduce execution time of a sequential IRACE search. Execution time decreased 72% when 8 parallel calls were allowed. The implementation monitored available resources and avoided overloading hardware components. Experiments showed that the degree of parallelism is constrained not only by the number of parallel processes and GPU memory, but also the number of surviving configurations in a race. This indicates that the implementation is suitable for IRACE searches where a high number of configurations is desired to be sampled in each race. In all experiments good quality images were generated during the search process.

The main lines for future work include implementing a new version of the Execution Manager using more advanced inter process communication techniques to reduce idle time of Lipizzaner processes and GPU resources. Other interesting line is studying the search capabilities of IRACE with an extended computational budget and a larger number of configuration candidates per race. The proposed solution should also be applied to more complex problems using a bigger population of generator and discriminator networks in Lipizzaner.

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